

An Assessment of Guidance and Counselling Services for B.Ed. Students at Lucknow University: Current Practices and Challenges

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Abstract

This research paper examines the current scenario of guidance and counselling services at the graduate level in Lucknow University. It explores the awareness, accessibility and availability of these services through quantitative analyses. This study adopted a descriptive survey research design. Population of study was students of B.Ed. course studying in Lucknow University. Simple Random and Stratified Sampling was used to select the students. The instrument used to collect data for the study was a self-made questionnaire. The data was analysed using descriptive statistics such as t-test and represented through table and graph. Findings indicated that there is sufficient awareness about availability and importance of Guidance and Counselling Services among B.Ed. students and how they enhance the overall effectiveness of these services in supporting graduate students' mental, academic and personal development.

Keywords Guidance and Counselling Services , Lucknow University, Awareness.

Introduction

Guidance and counselling services play a pivotal role in fostering the holistic well-being of individuals across various stages of life. As humans navigate the complexities of existence, they encounter a multitude of challenges that can impede their emotional, social, and psychological equilibrium. In this essay, we'll explore the fundamental need for guidance and counselling services and how they contribute to enhancing human well-being.

Firstly, it's essential to acknowledge that life is inherently unpredictable, characterised by constant changes and uncertainties. Individuals often grapple with personal issues such as relationship conflicts, career dilemmas, self-esteem issues, and mental health concerns. Without adequate support and guidance, these challenges can exacerbate, leading to emotional distress, reduced productivity, and diminished quality of life. Guidance and counselling services provide a safe and supportive environment for individuals to explore their concerns, gain insight into their experiences, and develop coping strategies to navigate life's complexities effectively.

In summary, guidance and counselling services in higher education play a critical role in promoting student success, well-being, and empowerment. By addressing the diverse needs of students, these services contribute to a supportive and inclusive academic environment, ultimately leading to improved student outcomes and a more successful and fulfilling higher education experience.

Problem Formulation

Every person will require assistance at some point in their lives; some may require it continuously while others will only require it during difficult times. This means that some sort of clear direction is required. "The concept of guidance is a set of activities that has given us a way out of the many issues we face in this day and age of advanced scientific and technological advancement." et al. Bassey (2007) Counselling and guidance are

services that help people make wise decisions and life adjustments. Programs for guidance and counselling are intended to help adolescents with their academic, social, emotional, and physical challenges.

The need for counseling in Indian schools is made clear by the rise in suicide instances and psychiatric issues among pupils. The emotional safety net that the majority of Indian families had previously offered has been diminished by shifting family patterns, like divorces, single parent households, and operating moms. The younger generations are growing less tolerant, abusive, and cooperative. In this regard, counselling appears to be a successful approach. Students typically deal with social-personal issues, emotional inadequacy, and acceptable career choices. Guidance and counselling help students better understand and embrace themselves, their personalities, endowment, strengths and weaknesses, attitudes, and worth as unique individuals in order to overcome all sorts of life's deficiencies (Arowolo, 2013).

Objective of study The objective of the study is to evaluate the awareness among graduate students regarding the availability and importance of guidance and counselling services.

Review of Literature

Guidance and counselling services in universities have been extensively studied, with a consensus on their importance in promoting students' academic success and personal well-being. Studies suggest that well-implemented guidance and counselling programs can lead to improved academic performance, reduced dropout rates, and enhanced mental health among students. However, the effectiveness of these services often depends on factors such as availability, accessibility, quality of counselling staff, and institutional support.

ISSRA(2022): Implementation of guidance and counselling services during the COVID-19 pandemic. This is study in to describe how counselling services were implemented during the COVID-19 pandemic and it also shifted our focus towards the mental health concerns such as depression, sleep deprivation and anxiety. All of which have a detrimental effect on students, motivation for academic success and generate behavioural issues in the schools.

The acceptance of school counsellors in the use of ICT during school from home in the COVID-19 era(2020): This study focuses on the importance of digital transformation in the school counselling is the basic concept of acceptance. Without acceptance by school counsellors, there can be no digital transformation in guidance and counselling services. If a school counsellors cannot optimise technology, the guidance and counselling services process will potentially become a gap that triggers the lack of a student motivation. This is to measure the participation value of the school counsellor who has used ICT with analysis parameters : Computer Anxiety/Self- efficacy/Collegial collaboration/Lack facility/ Perceived Easeof use/ Perceived usefulness.

Methodology The study adopted a descriptive survey design. This method is appropriate for obtaining factual and attitudinal information. This study seeks to obtain descriptive and self-reported information from students. Population of the study involves all students studying in B.Ed. Course in Lucknow University. The sample taken was 70 students studying in B.Ed. course in Lucknow University. There were a total of 38 boys and 32 girls from two different batches of B.Ed. students. Sample was chosen by using Stratified Random Sampling technique. The self-made questionnaire was used to collect the raw data. The questionnaire had closed-ended items.

Result and Discussion

Data was collected by use of a self-made questionnaire. The collected data was analysed. Results were presented for the objective and were interpreted and discussed.

To evaluate the awareness among graduate students regarding the availability and importance of guidance and counselling services.

Table no. 1 Mental health and academic concerns of students regarding the Awareness of Guidance and Counselling Services

Confidence Interval :

Mean of Group 1 minus Group 2 = 14.5000

95% Confidence Interval of this difference from = 46.4276 to 17.4267

Intermediate values used in calculations:

t = 1.0739

df = 7

standard error of difference = 13.502

GROUP	NO. OF QUES. N	MEAN	STD. DEV SD	STD. ERROR	CALCULATED t-VALUE	TABLE t-VALUE	REMARKS AT 0.05 LEVEL OF SIGNIFICANCE
GROUP 1 (Mental Health)	3	165.00	20.00	13.502	1.073	2.365	SIGNIFICANT
GROUP 2 (Academic Concern)	6	179.50	18.72				

Fig. 1 Graphical representation of the data

In the present study, the statistical evaluation of the data obtained from the questionnaire, taking Question no. 8, 25, 35 of mental health and Question no. 1, 2, 3, 4, 21, 16 of academic concern regarding the awareness of Guidance and Counselling Services (Table no 1).

This provides the researcher with sufficient evidence to accept the null hypothesis. There is no significant difference between increased awareness of guidance and counselling services among students and greater utilisation of these services for addressing mental health and academic concerns.

Moreover, the mean difference of 1.073 is less than 2.365 at 0.05 level, so the null hypothesis is accepted at 0.05 level.

The difference between the mean score of the awareness of guidance and counselling services among students and utilisation of these services for addressing mental health and academic concerns is not significant. Hence, there is no significant difference in the means of the two samples.

Conclusion

With the present study, we can conclude that the students studying in B.Ed. courses of Lucknow University are very much aware about the Guidance and Counselling Services and how these services can help them in getting proper solutions for the problems related to their mental health and academic concerns, they may face while studying as well as in their personal life. These services can be of great help as every individual at some point needs someone with more knowledge and experience to guide them out of their problems. And with proper awareness and availability of these services students can freely rely on the institution for better guidance. Even though with all the facilities available, there is

still room for improvement when it comes to the incorporation of Guidance and Counselling Services.

Incorporating comprehensive guidance and counselling services into the curriculum is crucial for the holistic development of students, as it addresses their mental health needs, enhances their livelihoods, and equips them with essential skills for effective adjustment. Awareness about these services ensures that students understand the support available to them, encouraging proactive engagement with their well-being. Moreover, making these services readily available within educational institutions ensures timely intervention and support during times of academic, personal, or emotional challenges.

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